

USL proposals to the governments of the South Asian and Sub-Saharan African countries, and the African Union (Draft 1)

By Dongchan Lee

Date: January 13th, 2015

ABSTRACT

USL1 proposals to the governments of the South Asian and African countries, and the African Union as a part of larger program called 5UE for 5 regions or continents proposal (to governments & the UN) will operate under the principle of 5UEs. **The key idea** of us is to trigger peaceful global revolution using the established human capital boost factors of USL (which literally will trigger the educational revolution in very short time). As the sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia overall are the least economically developed regions in the world, the economic boosts on these regions based on USL1 will be much larger than the rest of the world. Over the next 60-80 years of time frame, USL1 can literally boost the economy 100 times of the current GDPs of these regions. Using that potential, we are trying to establish an UN-led international treaty and create URF (Unified Redistribution Fund), which is designed to boost the globally sustainable prosperity in the following sequence: **Unified 5 Es (Education → Economy → Energy → Environment → Empowerment)**. As of now, we are planning to use a simple version of USL1 called UBN1 (Universal Basic Numeracy) the projections of the economic growths, narrowing economic gaps are included at the end.

INTRODUCTION

USL-5UE-URF Trio is our attempt to transform our world to much a better world. This paper for the USL1 proposals to the governments of the South Asian and African countries, and the African Union is **a part of larger program called 5UE for 5 regions or continents proposal (to governments & the UN)** for which you can find the details at <http://uslglobal.com/blog/5ue-for-5-continents-proposal-to-governments-the-un/> Also, We strongly suggest you to look at [U Trio introduction page](#) as our overarching schemes may be a bit overwhelming to the first encounters to our plans. Please try to check out the video introductions and USL evidences so that we can start communicating for your countries, for the African Union.

To achieve the main objectives of USL-5UE-URF, we need the full scope of collaborations from the governments of all levels, the UN, NGOs, Social Enterprises, etc.

This will revolutionize all in 5 Es and will benefit every country on earth profoundly, but the two regions that will benefit the most are Africa (especially the Sub-Saharan Africa) and South Asia, followed by Central America as these regions seemed to be less developed compared to the rest of the world overall. Our goals are closely aligned with those of the UN's, especially the Millennium Development Goals and the Sustainable Energy for All (SE4All).

THE ORIGIN

The whole thing started with **USL (Unified Super Learning)**. With USL, the average people learn math & physical sciences 10-20+ times faster (advancing 5+ Standard Deviations or compressing 11+ years of math in 1/2-1 year for the average students without harder work or study), meaning the average students can learn 12 years of math in 0.5-1 year, 4-10 times faster than the fastest learning math prodigies in the entire world. **This has explosive economic growth implications as we'll explain shortly.**

The GDP growth comparisons for the 6 economic Clusters Projections After USL1 reforms takes place within 5 years: These huge boost of the GDP is the clue and glue that this can contribute to the 5UE revolutions are possible for the benefits of all

As you can see the projections of the GDP growths between the expected GDP sizes without USL1 vs. those with USL1 reforms.

A quick summary on USL-5UEs-URF:

- the 6 fundamental questions (Who, When, Where, What, How, Why) with regard to USL-5UE-URF Trio
- USL (to trigger the massive national, regional, and global human capital transformations as its contribution potential is larger than the entire world economic size in 10-20 years)

- Mechanisms behind the massive economic boosts: [USL 1.0 solutions for the top 5 global challenges or crises](#) (The complete transition to the renewable energy + Sovereign Debts + Environment (Climate change included) + Post-2015 + stagnating education crises to resolve them all in 10-20 years once the 5 year reforms of the USL1 is complete.)
- [A quasi-Moore's Law for the relationship between human capital and the economic growth \(this is the critical part to relate the revolutionary USL with the economic growths\)](#)
- Due to the staggering economic implications with the USL initiatives, all the countries and their governments – be it the least developed or the OECD, G20 countries – **the governments will have the economic, from the human capital perspectives, incentives to join and prosper instead of becoming obsolete and getting behind the rest of the participating countries, over the next a decade.**
- **5UE** (United 5Es: Education → Economy → Energy → Environment → Empowerment) to lay foundations for the sustainable, renewable energy-based, resource-based, and circular circular economy based on the USL contribution factors to only member nations that are

willing to grow themselves in exchange of the collaborative supports to the rest of the world based on the 5UE principles.)

- **URF** (that we are trying to collaborate with governments to create a bindable international treaty and create URF which is Unified Redistribution Funds that boost all 5UEs together.)

UBN1 for the regions

Universal Basic Numeracy (UBN) is a USL proposal of teaching rapid arithmetic to sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, etc., to reduce the extreme poverty very rapidly while providing the renewable energy infrastructures to all participating schools. During these, with the authentic collaborations and verifications of the participating governments and the UN, we can help both the participating governments and the UN (especially for the post-2015 and SE4All), let alone the people at the same time. This project may provide the blueprints for the URF (after the creation of the USL-based new international treaty with the UN) later on.

EVIDENCES FOR USL

As you may like to see some evidences for the effectiveness of the USL pilot studies...

Channel 30 (Santa Lucia Uatlan, Solola, Guatemala) news on February 23rd on Sunday, 2014 (5 minutes long) with the English subtitle (for which you need to click at the bottom of the video for Caption and choose English). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TDXEoR38fuI> You may skip the first 40 seconds. (With the English subtitle.)

For [the transcripts of this in English translation, click here.](#)

For the overwhelming evidences of USL upon which the entire schemes for the 5UEs are based, please check the [Overwhelming video evidences in support of the USL](#) (Please check them especially if you are an education professional or education economist.)

The economic incentives why all the African governments and the African Union should pay attention to the proposals of USL-5UE-URF?

NOTE: to view the clearer pictures and charts, please click to them.

1) 3-tier Economic Growth Projections , depending on the average annual economic growth rates

2) The economic incentives of USL to the less developed countries

Sub-Saharan GDP growth Projrvyionns for the next 60 yrs with vs. without USL-URF1

The projected South Asian GDP boost with the USL-URF1

1. The recent average GDP growth rates of the African and South Asian countries are about 5% (4-6% overall), to double the economy, it will take 15 years. If 6% average will take 12 years. If 4%, 18 years.

2. USL (with URF 1) will add 2-3% in the annual growth rates your GDPs, and for 7%, will take 10.25 years and if 8%, 9 years, meaning that your economy will double in 1/3 less time at least over the next 10 years the very least. So it is more likely you will double your growth speed next 10 years, and this is only the beginning.
3. In 15 years with the average African growths, most likely your country's economy will be doubled than without. With the USL-URF, you are more likely triple your income in 15 years instead of doubling.
4. Over the next 50 years alone, even if you linearize the surplus economic growths with this alone will average 70% – 500% more economy each year for half a decade, depending on where you are.

Projected scenarios if the URF1 becomes a reality

More specific break downs:

For the general introduction to what we are trying to do, please check these pages.

1. [USL-5ues-urf-trio-introduction/](#)
2. [5UEs intro](#)

So please browse through the introduction pages and we hope to hear from you soon as soon as possible so that we can **start communicating bilaterally and multi-laterally**. This is very important because the MDGs of the UN ends in 2015 and we hope to establish the new international treaty via the UN in 2015.

REFERENCES